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The first insight of environmental change impact on Syrphidae (Diptera) morphology: wing fluctuating asymmetry analysis of *Merodon aberrans* Egger, 1860

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Throughout Earth's history, climate has changed continuously, but at a much slower pace than currently observed. In Serbia average temperature increase over the territory is 1.2 °C for the period 1996-2015 with respect to the period 1961-1980, with the highest increase of maximum daily temperature during the summer season, 2.2 °C. Climate change is a complicated phenomenon, with various changes including shifts in limits (maxima and minima), average conditions, and variance, which can all be measured at different temporal and spatial scales. Insects are ectothermic and critically depend on environmental temperature throughout all aspects of their life history, but also other niche aspects are changing—precipitation, humidity, cloud cover, weather extremes, biotic interactions—with potentially dramatic impacts.

Our research delves into a relatively unexplored area, as there is currently no insight into the impact of environmental change on the Syrphidae morphology. To investigate this, we selected populations from a single natural habitat with insignificant anthropogenic influence. The impact of environmental change on Syrphidae morphology was measured through fluctuating asymmetry (FA) of wing shape. FA represents slight and random deviations from bilateral symmetry normally distributed around a 0 mean. Increased FA reflects the stress an organism undergoes during development, which may be caused by environmental and genetic stress.

We studied populations of *Merodon aberrans* Egger, 1860 from the Vršac Mountains, Serbia, from the 1980s and 2020s, and compared the wing asymmetry between these two temporal populations. Results showed that the 2020s population exhibited greater wing FA compared to the 1980s population, with a statistically significant difference. These indicate that environmental change affects the asymmetry of hoverflies, which, according to numerous studies, is negatively correlated with organism fitness. Further studies are crucial to expand this analysis to other species within this family, encompassing all forms of larval development if feasible, and to compare their response to environmental change.

Keywords: environmental change, fluctuating asymmetry, hoverfly, temporal populations, wing shape

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